

EFFECT OF LOADING DIRECTION ON COMPRESSION FATIGUE BEHAVIOR OF IMPACT-DAMAGED CFRP LAMINATES

N. Uda and K. Ono

Department of Aeronautics and Astronautics, Kyushu University
744 Motoooka, Nishi-ku, Fukuoka 819-0395, Japan
uda@aero.kyushu-u.ac.jp

SUMMARY

The objective of this study is to investigate failure mechanisms of impact-damaged CFRP laminates subjected to cyclic compression with different loading directions. Compression-after-impact tests and post-impact compression fatigue tests of quasi-isotropic laminates were conducted with on- and off-axis loadings. The off-axis cyclic loading caused free-edge delamination independently of the impact damage.

Keywords: Fatigue, Failure, Compression, Impact, Damage

INTRODUCTION

The application of composite materials to aircraft primary structures is increasing due to their lightweight and high strength. However, the excellent mechanical properties of composite materials can be significantly reduced by a low velocity impact, such as tools dropped during maintenance and runway stones during taxiing. The compression-after-impact (CAI) strength of composite structures, in particular, is seriously reduced even if impact damage is not detectable by visual inspection. A number of investigations, e.g., [1-5] have been conducted to estimate the sensitivity of the CAI strength to low velocity impact damage. The fatigue behavior of impacted composite laminates has also been studied extensively during the past couple of decades, e.g., [6-14]. However, the effect of damage growth mechanisms on post-impact fatigue response has not been fully understood and an effective damage-tolerance methodology of post-impact composite laminates has not been established. The objective of this study is to investigate failure mechanisms of impact-damaged CFRP laminates subjected to cyclic compression with different loading directions. Some of the experimental observations obtained by post-impact compression fatigue tests are reported.

EXPERIMENTS

Specimens

The composite systems used in these experiments were UT500/Epoxy (Toho Tenax, QU135-197A). The layups used were $[+45/0/-45/90]_{3s}$ and $[+22.5/-22.5/-67.5/+67.5]_{3s}$. Compression tests of $[+22.5/-22.5/-67.5/+67.5]_{3s}$ correspond to ones of $[+45/0/-45/90]_{3s}$

loaded in the +22.5-deg direction. The layup [+45/0/-45/90]_{ns} is most commonly used in CAI tests, e.g., [1,5]. We evaluated the effect of loading direction on the CAI and post-impact fatigue strengths of the composite laminates by using these two layups. 300 x 300 mm panels were fabricated by a hot press machine in our laboratory according to the prepreg manufacturer's recommended cure cycle. After fabrication, each panel was inspected using an ultrasonic C-scan system, GNES G-Scan 6AX500, to ensure good quality. Specimens that were 135 mm long and 50 mm wide were cut from the 4.5 mm thick laminates. In consideration of the loading capacity limit of 100 kN of the Instron 8501 fatigue testing machine, the width of the unimpacted specimens was reduced to 25 mm. For simplicity, the [+45/0/-45/90]_{3S} specimens are called "on-axis" specimens while the [+22.5/-22.5/-67.5/+67.5]_{3S} specimens are "off-axis".

Impact Tests

Impact tests were performed using a drop-weight test rig with an impactor having a 12 mm diameter hemispherical tip. The specimen was clamped between two plates, each with a 35 mm diameter circular window. The impactor was captured on the rebound after impact to prevent secondary strikes. The impactor velocity was measured using a laser displacement sensor. The impact energy was defined as the kinetic energy of the impactor just at the moment of first contact with the specimen. The impact energy is normalized by dividing by the thickness of the specimen. The normalized impact energy level was 0.58–2.02 J/mm in this study. The damage area induced by the impact load was tested using the ultrasonic C-scan system based on the pulse-echo method.

Static and Fatigue Tests

Static compression tests and compression fatigue tests were conducted in the servo-hydraulic testing machine with an end-loading fixture as shown in Fig. 1, which was built based on Shimokawa et al.'s study [15]. The specimen was placed in the fixture without tabs and was tightly clamped with binding grips. This fixture does not have an anti-buckling device as prescribed by ASTM D 695, but prevents an out-of-plane directional movement of the specimen by a pair of supporting guides for the whole of the fixture. The compression load is applied through end-sections of the specimen with the binding grips. A gage length of 35 mm for the compression specimen was selected to prevent global buckling of the unimpacted specimen at the initial stage of loading.

The compression-compression fatigue tests were conducted at 1 Hz with constant-amplitude sinusoidal loading, under ambient laboratory conditions. The maximum compressive stress of the cyclic loading was chosen to be 65-90% of the ultimate static strength, or the residual static strength for the impacted specimens. The minimum compressive stress during fatigue was fixed at 2.5 MPa for avoiding machine instabilities. Our experiments were intended to conduct the compression-compression fatigue tests with the stress ratio of $R = \infty$. In some cases, monitoring of the damage progression during fatigue was performed periodically using the ultrasonic inspection system to assess the change of the damaged area as a function of the number of load cycles.

Figure 1. Compression test fixture. (a) Actual. (b) Schematic.

EXPERIMENTAL RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Impact Damage

The impact-induced damage was principally manifested in the form of delaminations. Figure 2 shows the ultrasonic C-scan images of damage induced in an on-axis specimen subjected to a 1.91 J/mm impact. The C-scan images in Fig. 2a and b were taken from the impacted side and the backside of the specimen, respectively. The depths of the delaminations are indicated using the color gradation shown at the right of Fig. 2. The delaminations are formed in a spiral-stair manner in the through-the-thickness direction with each step corresponding to a change in ply orientation. Therefore, the spiral direction is clockwise from the impacted side through the midplane and changes to counterclockwise below the midplane. The delamination size was measured by image processing. Figure 3 shows the delamination size at each interface. In Fig. 3, the delamination size is represented as the diameter of a hypothetical circle on the assumption that the envelope of the damaged area was circular at each interface. The delamination size increased away from the impacted front face until the interface between the 19th 0-deg ply and the 20th +45-deg ply, and then decreased toward the backside, as shown in Figs. 2 and 3.

Ishikawa and Suemasu [1] introduced an effective diameter D_e for a unified description of CAI strength behavior obtained by various CAI test methods. The effective diameter D_e is defined as the average diameter of the hypothetical circle with equivalent area to the delamination geometry. We also adopt the parameter D_e normalized by the width b of the specimen to describe the size of the impact-induced delaminations.

Figure 4 shows the relationships between the effective diameter of delaminations D_e and the normalized impact energy. In the impact tests, the specimen was supported by the two plates with the circular window. Therefore, there is no difference between the impact tests of the on-axis and off-axis specimens. The circular laminates with the same stacking sequence were laterally impacted, so the on-axis and off-axis specimens resulted in the same relationship, which indicates the delamination appears to vary linearly with impact energy above a threshold impact energy, as shown in the Fig. 4.

Figure 2. C-scan images of an on-axis specimen subjected to a 1.91 J/mm impact: (a) Impacted side and (b) backside.

Figure 3. Delamination size at each interface of an on-axis specimen subjected to a 1.91 J/mm impact.

Figure 4. Relationships between effective delamination diameter and normalized impact energy.

CAI Strength

Figure 5 depicts the CAI strength of the laminates. The abscissa is the normalized impact energy. The compressive strengths of the unimpacted specimens were on average 642 MPa for the on-axis case and 521 MPa for the off-axis case. Figure 6 shows the CAI strength normalized by the ultimate strength of the unimpacted specimens as a function of the normalized effective diameter of delaminations. The CAI strengths of the on-axis and off-axis specimens were reduced to about 40% and 60% of the unimpacted strengths, respectively. The compressive strength of the off-axis specimens without impact is lower than that of the on-axis specimens. The CAI strength of the off-axis specimens is, however, less decreased than that of the on-axis specimens. The off-axis specimen without impact caused the free-edge delamination before the ultimate failure as marked by a circle in Fig. 7. On the other hand, the unimpacted on-axis specimens were abruptly fractured without preliminary failure such as free-edge delamination. The cylindrical-shaped attachment by the specimen in Fig. 7 is a support jig of an AE (acoustic emission) sensor.

Figure 5. CAI strength as a function of normalized impact energy.

Figure 6. Normalized CAI strength as a function of normalized effective diameter of delaminations.

Figure 7. Photograph of a free-edge delamination caused in an off-axis specimen without impact.

Post-Impact Compression Fatigue Behavior

S-N curves

Post-impact fatigue test data were processed in the form of relationships between maximum compressive stress and number of cycles to fracture (*S-N* curves). Figure 8 depicts the compression fatigue test data of the specimens sorted into several groups by the size of the effective delamination diameter. The *S-N* relationships for the on-axis and off-axis specimens are shown by solid and open symbols, respectively, in Fig. 8. Figure 8 indicates that as the amount of impact damage was increased, the compression fatigue performance of the laminates decreased.

In order to clarify the amount of fatigue strength degradation, the *S-N* curves are plotted using an ordinate normalized by the CAI strengths of the specimens with the same damage size, as shown in Fig. 9. The off-axis specimens exhibited more steeply declining *S-N* curves than those of the on-axis specimens. The specimens with larger impact damage showed a gentler *S-N* gradient.

Figure 8. S–N curves sorted by the size of the effective delamination diameter.

Figure 9. Normalized maximum compressive stress as a function of cycle number to fracture.

Specimen deformation during fatigue

In the case of the unimpacted specimens, no large out-of-plane deflection was observed during fatigue. Figure 10 shows photographs of an unimpacted off-axis specimen under fatigue loading. The specimen was cyclically subjected to a maximum compressive stress of 340 MPa. The number of cycles to fracture of this specimen was 3693. Separations of the thin surface layer at the free edge on the both front and back sides of the specimen were observed, as indicated by the circles in Fig. 10a. The specimen was abruptly broken during the 3693rd loading as shown in Fig. 10b. On the other hand, the on-axis specimens without impact did not show free-edge delamination failure before the final fracture. The unimpacted on-axis specimens were catastrophically fractured in a similar manner to Fig. 10b.

Figure 11 shows photographs of an impacted on-axis specimen during fatigue loading. This specimen was subjected to a 1.59 J/mm impact resulting in delaminations with $D_e/b = 0.55$, and subsequently cyclically loaded to a maximum compressive stress of 217 MPa. The number of cycles to fracture of this specimen was 37750. An adhesive white tape was wrapped around the specimen to attach the AE sensor as shown in Fig. 11. Figure 11a shows the delamination extended from the impact damage site to the free edge at the back surface of impact and the delaminated sublaminates were locally deformed in the out-of-plane direction at the 37700th loading. Figure 11b shows the fractured specimen at the 37750th loading.

Figure 12 shows an impacted off-axis specimen during fatigue loading. This specimen was subjected to a 0.88 J/mm impact resulting in delaminations with $D_e/b = 0.24$, and subsequently cyclically loaded to a maximum compressive stress of 280 MPa. The

number of cycles to fracture of this specimen was 24942. Separations of the thin surface layer at the free edge on the both impacted and back sides of the specimen were observed at the 20001st loading, as indicated by the yellow circles in Fig. 12a. Fibers were broken in the +22.5-deg ply at the back surface and matrix cracks occurred at the back surface as shown by the red circles in the same photograph. These matrix cracks extended to the edge of the binding grip during fatigue. Figure 12b shows the fractured specimen at the 24942nd loading.

Figure 10. Photographs of an unimpacted off-axis specimen in fatigue. (Fatigue life of this specimen was 3693.) (a) $N = 2856$ and (b) $N = 3693$.

Figure 11. Photographs of an impacted on-axis specimen with $D_e/b = 0.55$ in fatigue. (Fatigue life of this specimen was 37750.) (a) Backside at $N = 37700$ and (b) backside at $N = 37750$.

Figure 12. Photographs of an impacted off-axis specimen with $D/b = 0.24$ in fatigue. (Fatigue life of this specimen was 24942.) (a) Backside at $N = 20001$ and (b) backside at $N = 24942$.

Damage growth during fatigue

Some specimens were inspected using the pulse-echo system to assess damage progression during fatigue.

Figure 13 shows delamination growth behavior of the impacted on-axis specimen, the impact-induced delaminations of which were shown in Figs. 2 and 3. This specimen was subjected to a 1.91 J/mm impact, as mentioned above, that caused the delaminations with $D/b = 0.46$, and subsequently cyclically loaded to a maximum compressive stress of 244 MPa. Figures 13a, b and c indicate echo level view at each interply detected by the ultrasonic C-scanning of the specimen just after the impact, the 413th and 16468th cyclic loading, respectively. In Figs. 13a, b and c, the left four images show C-scan results from the back side of the specimen, the right four images are from the impacted side, respectively. The loading direction is up and down in Fig. 13. Examination of the C-scan images in Figs. 13a and b reveals that the impact-induced delamination grew widthwise at the 21st 90-deg/22nd -45-deg ply interface on the back side of the specimen during the fatigue test. And some damage occurred in the 22nd -45-deg and 23rd 0-deg plies at the edge of the 21st 90-deg/22nd -45-deg interply delamination as shown in Fig. 13b. Figure 13c shows the delamination between the 22nd -45-deg and the 23rd 0-deg ply reached the free edge, and the delaminations on the back side propagated in the loading direction to the edge of the binding grip.

Figure 14 shows delamination growth behavior of the impacted off-axis specimen, the deformation of which was shown in Fig. 12. Figures 14a, b and c indicate C-scan results of the specimen just after the impact, the 3389th and 20001st cyclic loading, respectively. Examination of the C-scan images in Figs. 14a and b reveals that the impact-induced damage grew widthwise at the 21st +67.5-deg/22nd -67.5-deg, 22nd -67.5-deg/23rd -22.5-deg, and 23rd -22.5-deg/24th +22.5-deg ply interfaces during the fatigue test. And the free-edge delamination occurred at the 1st +22.5-deg/2nd -22.5-deg and 23rd -22.5-deg/24th +22.5-deg interfaces independently of the impact-induced damage. As shown in Fig. 14c, the free-edge delaminations were largely extended, and the impact-induced delamination on the back side propagated in the loading direction to the edge of the binding grip.

Figure 13. C-scan images of the on-axis specimen. (The impact-induced delaminations of this specimen were shown in Figs. 2 and 3 as well.) (a) $N = 0$ (i.e. just after impact) (b) $N = 413$ (c) $N = 16468$.

Figure 14. C-scan images of the off-axis specimen. (The deformation of this specimen was shown in Fig. 12.) (a) $N = 0$ (i.e. just after impact) (b) $N = 3389$ (c) $N = 20001$.

CONCLUSIONS

1. The compressive strength of the off-axis specimens without impact is lower than that of the on-axis specimens. The CAI strength of the off-axis specimens is, however, less decreased than that of the on-axis specimens.
2. The off-axis specimens exhibited more steeply declining S–N curves than those of the on-axis specimens. The specimens with larger impact damage showed a gentler S–N gradient.
3. In the case of the on-axis specimens, the impact-induced delamination grew widthwise on the back side of the specimen during the fatigue test. And some damage occurred at the edge of the delamination on the back side of the specimen. The delamination reached the free edge, and propagated in the loading direction to the edge of the binding grip during fatigue.
4. In the case of the off-axis specimens, the free-edge delamination occurred independently of the impact-induced damage during the fatigue test. The impact-induced delamination grew widthwise on the back side of the specimen. The free-edge delaminations were largely extended, and the impact-induced delamination on the back side propagated in the loading direction to the edge of the binding grip during fatigue.

ACKNOWLEDGEMENTS

The authors would like to thank Y. Morimoto, K. Watanabe, R. Yamashita, Y. Kouno, K. Yamamoto and T. Saruno for their assistance in the experimental work and valuable discussions.

References

1. Ishikawa T, Suemasu H. Clarification of mechanical behavior in compression after impact (CAI) and open hole compression (OHC) tests for carbon/polymer composites. In: Proceedings of tenth US–Japan conference on composite Materials, Stanford, CA, USA, 2002. p. 21–32.
2. Suemasu H, Osada Y, Wakabayashi H. Compressive behavior of composite laminates with different size multiple delaminations. In: Proceedings of ICCM-13, Beijing, China, 2001. ID-1654.
3. Davies GAO, Zhang X. Impact damage prediction in carbon composite structures. *Int J Impact Eng* 1995;16:149–70.
4. Soutis C, Curtis PT. Prediction of the post-impact compressive strength of CFRP laminated composites. *Compos Sci Technol* 1996;56:677–84.
5. Zhou G, Rivera LA. Investigation for the reduction of in-plane compressive strength in preconditioned thin composite panels. *J Compos Mater* 2005;39:391–422.
6. Byers BA. Behavior of damaged graphite/epoxy laminates under compression loading. NASA CR-159293, 1980.
7. Swanson SR, Cairns DS, Gyll ME, Johnson D. Compression fatigue response for carbon fiber with conventional and toughened epoxy matrices with damage. *ASME J Eng Mater Technol* 1993;115:116–21.
8. Ding YQ, Yan Y, McIlhagger R. Effect of impact and fatigue loads on the strength of plain weave carbon–epoxy composites. *J Mater Process Technol* 1995;55:58–62.
9. Beheshty MH, Harris B. A constant-life model of fatigue behaviour for carbonfibre composites: the effect of impact damage. *Compos Sci Technol* 1998;58:9–18.
10. Mitrovic M, Hahn HT, Carman GP, Shyprykevich P. Effect of loading parameters on the fatigue behavior of impact damaged composite laminates. *Compos Sci Technol* 1999;59:2059–78.
11. Chen AS, Almond DP, Harris B. Impact damage growth in composites under fatigue conditions monitored by acoustography. *Int J Fatigue* 2002;24:257–61.
12. Melin LG, Schön J, Nyman T. Fatigue testing and buckling characteristics of impacted composite specimens. *Int J Fatigue* 2002;24:263–72.
13. Katerelos DG, Paipetis A, Kostopoulos V. A simple model for the prediction of the fatigue delamination growth of impacted composite panels. *Fatigue Fract Eng Mater Struct* 2004;27:911–22.
14. Butler R, Almond DP, Hunt GW, Hu B, Gathercole N. Compressive fatigue limit of impact damaged composite laminates. *Compos: Part A* 2007;38:1211–5.
15. Shimokawa T, Hamaguchi Y, Kakuta Y, Katoh H, Sanda T, Mizuno H, et al. Effect of isothermal aging on ultimate strength of high-temperature composite materials for SST structures. *J Compos Mater* 1999;33:1104–18.